

TOWARDS MODERN KNOWLEDGE: WAYS TO IMPROVE THE SOFTWARE AND ITS EFFECTIVENESS IN DEVELOPING INFORMATION LITERACY SKILLS OF SENIOR PUPILS IN PRESIDENTIAL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. *This article discusses the role of software tools in the formation and development of information literacy of senior pupils (grades 10–11) in presidential educational institutions and ways to improve them. In an era of rapid development of digital technologies, improving pupils' knowledge, skills and qualifications in searching, analyzing, sorting and presenting information is one of the main directions of modern education. The article discusses software tools (Google Scholar, Mendeley, Canva, Prezi, Piktochart, MindMeister, etc.) that serve to develop information literacy, their effectiveness, and the opportunities created for teachers and pupils. It also provides recommendations for developing software tools suitable for the national education system, improving digital literacy, and integrating curricula with modern technologies.*

Keywords: *information literacy, presidential educational institutions, software, digital literacy, high school pupils, critical thinking, interactive learning, pupil independence, artificial intelligence tools, innovations in education, teacher qualifications, modern educational technologies, digitalization of the educational process, educational efficiency, national learning platforms*

Introduction: Today, in an era where digital technologies have deeply penetrated all spheres of our lives, the formation of pupils' skills to work effectively with information has become a pressing issue. Especially for pupils in grades 10-11 studying at Presidential educational institutions, these competencies serve as a key factor not only in deeper study of subjects, but also in the development of independent thinking, analysis, critical approach and creativity.

What is information literacy? Information literacy is the ability of a student to search for, analyze, select, evaluate, store, and effectively use relevant information from a variety of sources. This competency includes the following skills:

Identify and search for necessary information in a problematic situation;

- Critically analyze sources;
- Distinguish between real and fake information;
- Create information and present it in an understandable form;
- Develop a culture of using information technologies.

Opportunities of presidential educational institutions: Presidential schools, creative schools and specialized schools have a significant advantage over other general education schools with a modern educational and methodological base, classrooms equipped with advanced technologies, and qualified teachers. These institutions are carrying out effective work on the development of information literacy competencies through the following methods:

- STEAM approach: Solving real-life problems using information based on interdisciplinary integration;
- Digital literacy classes: Teaching pupils skills such as choosing reliable sources on the Internet, information security, and digital etiquette;
- Project work: Pupils independently test their skills in collecting, analyzing, and presenting information in real projects;
- Corporate libraries and online resources: Pupils have access to an expanded information base.

Factors for achieving effectiveness: The effectiveness of developing this competency in presidential educational institutions depends on several factors:

Curriculum flexibility - The integration of new information technologies into the curriculum, i.e., the inclusion of STEAM, robotics, fundamentals of artificial intelligence, critical thinking, and media literacy. Subjects are taught and updated based on international standards (for example, harmonized with IB, Cambridge, etc.). Pupils have the opportunity to study in-depth topics of interest to them based on a creative and project-based approach.

Teacher qualifications - Teachers who are digitally literate, motivated, and able to encourage independent thinking of pupils.

Student activity and motivation - Ensuring active participation of pupils in the learning process through interactive, practical exercises.

The following exercises will help pupils develop their information literacy skills:

Exercise: Creating an interactive website using JavaScript, HTML, CSS:

1. Create the file of JavaScript (script.js):

```
document.getElementById("myButton").addEventListener("click", function() {  
    document.getElementById("output").innerText = "Salom, o'quvchi! Siz tugmani bosdingiz."  
});
```

2. Create a button in the file HTML:

```
<!DOCTYPE html>  
<html lang="uz">  
<head>  
    <meta charset="UTF-8">  
    <title>JavaScript Interaktivligi</title>  
</head>  
<body>  
    <button id="myButton">Ma'lumotni ko'rsatish</button>  
    <p id="output"></p>  
    <script src="script.js"></script>  
</body>  
</html>
```

3. Change the design of the website CSS. Create a file (styles.css):

```
css

body {
  font-family: Arial, sans-serif;
  background-color: #f4f4f4;
}

header {
  background-color: #333;
  color: white;
  padding: 10px;
  text-align: center;
}

nav ul {
  list-style-type: none;
}

nav li {
  display: inline;
  margin-right: 10px;
}

nav a {
  color: white;
  text-decoration: none;
}
```

Such exercises will help improve education for senior pupils in Presidential educational institutions based on information technologies and software, develop their innovative thinking, critical analysis and effective use of information.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the development of information literacy competencies of 10-11th grade pupils in Presidential educational institutions is the main guarantee not only of the quality of their education, but also of their future professional activity and life success. The effectiveness of the work carried out on the formation and improvement of these competencies will help pupils think independently, find their way in the modern information environment and become active participants in the digital society.

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